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Research Article

**TYPHOID FEVER: PATHOGENESIS AND IMMUNOLOGIC
CONTROL.**¹Dr Haris Ali, ²Dr Muhammad Ussam Butt, ³Dr Bushra Naz.¹MBBS, Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore., ²MBBS, Bahria University Medical and Dental College, Karachi., ³MBBS, Ameer Ud Din Medical College, Lahore.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Typhoid fever is a disease caused by Salmonella enterica serotypes paratyphi A, B, C, and Salmonella enterica serotype typhi, especially in humans. There are no non-human vectors for Typhoidal Salmonella. In over 50 percent of healthy volunteers, and inoculum as small as 100,000 typhus species causes infection. Usually, typhoid fever is a short-term febrile disease that needs a median hospitalization time of 6 days. It has few long-term sequelae and a 0.2 percent mortality risk when treated. Untreated typhoid fever is a lethal disease that persists for many weeks, often affecting the central nervous system, with long-term morbidity. Isolated extreme headaches that can be mimic meningitis, acute lobar pneumonia, isolated arthralgia, severe jaundice, urinary symptoms fever alone are the common symptoms of typhoid. A strain of S that is multi-drug resistant (MDR) to Chloramphenicol, ampicillin, and co-trimoxazole typhoids is often used in a patient admitted to hospital in Asia in the late 1980s, and later in Africa. Now in recent advancements, Azithromycin is used as the first-line oral treatment for typhoid fever.

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INTRODUCTION:

Typhoid fever, otherwise called enteric fever, is a possibly lethal multisystemic disease caused fundamentally by *Salmonella enterica* serotype Typhi and, less significantly, *S. enterica* serotypes paratyphi A, B, and C. The terms typhoid and enteric fever are generally used to depict both major serotypes. Typhoid fever has a wide assortment of introductions that range from a staggering multisystemic sickness to moderately minor instances of loose bowels with second rate fever. The exemplary introduction is fever, discomfort, diffuse stomach agony, and obstruction. Untreated typhoid fever may advance to daze, obtundation, intestinal discharge, gut hole, and demise inside the multi-month of beginning. Survivors might be left with long haul or perpetual neuropsychiatric complications. *S. typhi* has been a significant human microorganism for millennia, flourishing in states of helpless sterilization, swarming, and social tumult. It might have liable for the Great Plague of Athens toward the finish of the Peloponnesian War. [1] The name *S. typhi* is originated from the old Greek typhus that was known to cause fever and sickness. In the high-level phases of typhoid fever, the patient's degree of cognizance is blurred. Although anti-toxins have uniquely decreased the recurrence of typhoid fever in the created world, it stays endemic in non-industrial nations. [2] Note that a few essayists allude to typhoid and paratyphoid fever as particular conditions brought about by the typhi versus paratyphi serovars.

Pathophysiology:

All species of pathogenic *Salmonella*, present in the gut are flooded by phagocytic cells, which later on pass through mucosa and reached at the macrophages of lamina. *Salmonella* which is not causing typhoid is phagocytized by colon and distal ileum. With cost like receptor (TLR) – 5 and TLR-4/MD2/CD-14 complex, macrophages perceive microorganism related atomic examples (PAMPs, for example, flagella and lipopolysaccharides. Macrophages and intestinal epithelial cells at that point pull in T cells and neutrophils with interleukin 8 (IL-8), causing irritation and stifling the contamination. [3, 4] In differentiation to the nontyphoidal salmonellae, *S. typhi* and paratyphi enter the host's framework fundamentally through the distal ileum. They have specific fimbriae that hold fast to the epithelium over groups of lymphoid tissue in the ileum (Peyer patches), the fundamental hand-off point for macrophages going from the gut into the lymphatic framework. The microorganisms at that point incite their host macrophages to pull in more macrophages. [3] *S. typhi* has a Vi capsular antigen that covers

PAMPs, evading neutrophil-based aggravation, while the most widely recognized paratyphi serovar, paratyphi A, doesn't. This may clarify the more noteworthy infectivity of typhi contrasted and the greater part of its cousins. [5] Typhoidal salmonella co-select the macrophages' cell apparatus for their generation [6] as they are brought through the mesenteric lymph hubs to the thoracic pipe and the lymphatics and afterward through to the reticuloendothelial tissues of the liver, spleen, bone marrow, and lymph hubs. Once there, they delay and keep on increasing until some basic thickness is reached. A short time later, the microorganisms incite macrophage apoptosis, breaking out into the circulatory system to attack the remainder of the body. [4] The microbes at that point taint the gallbladder through one or the other bacteremia or direct expansion of contaminated bile. The outcome is that the creature reenters the gastrointestinal parcel in the bile and reinfects Peyer patches. Microbes that don't reinfect the host are commonly shed in the stool and are then accessible to taint different hosts. [2, 4] Chronic transporters are answerable for a significant part of the transmission of the life form. For long time when they are not showing any symptoms but still shed microorganism in the stool. The creatures sequester themselves either as a biofilm on gallstones or gallbladder epithelium or, maybe, intracellularly, inside the epithelium itself. [7] The microorganisms discharged by a solitary transporter may have different genotypes, making it hard to follow an episode to its cause. [8]

Risk Factors:

Typhoidal salmonella has no non-human vectors. An inoculum as little as 100,000 creatures of typhi causes contamination in over half of solid volunteers. [9] Paratyphi requires a lot higher inoculum to taint, and it is less endemic in country zones. Consequently, examples of transmission are marginally unique. Paratyphi is all the more regularly sent in food from road merchants. It is accepted that whatever nourishments give a benevolent climate to the microbe. Paratyphi is more normal among newcomers to metropolitan regions, presumably because they will in general be immunologically gullible to it. Additionally, voyagers get practically zero assurance against paratyphi from the current typhoid immunizations, all of which target typhi. [13, 14] Typhoidal salmonella can endure a stomach pH as low as 1.5. Acid neutralizers, histamine-2 receptor foes (H2 blockers), proton siphon inhibitors, gastrectomy, and achlorhydria decline stomach sharpness and encourage *S. typhi* contamination. [4]. HIV/AIDS is connected with an expanded danger of nontyphoidal *Salmonella* contamination; be that as

it may, the information and feelings in the writing regarding whether this is valid for *S typhi* or paratyphi disease are clashing. On the off chance that an affiliation exists, it is presumably minor. [15, 16, 17, 18] Other danger factors for typhoid fever incorporate different hereditary polymorphisms. These danger factors frequently additionally incline to other intracellular microbes. For example, code of protein PARK2 and PACGR that are used as a tool to separate macrophage reactions hosted by bacterial flagging atoms. Polymorphisms in their shared administrative area are discovered lopsidedly in people tainted with *Mycobacterium leprae* and *S typhi* [10, 11]. On the other hand, defensive host changes likewise exist. Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance receptor (CFTR) link in vitro with the *S typhi* fimbriae, which is interconnected to the film of gut. Two to 5% of white people are heterozygous for the CFTR transformation F508del, which is related to a diminished weakness to typhoid fever, just as to cholera and tuberculosis. The homozygous F508del transformation in CFTR is related to cystic fibrosis. Hence, typhoid fever may add to the transformative weight that keeps a consistent event of cystic fibrosis, similarly as intestinal sickness keeps up sickle cell infection in Africa. [19, 20] As the working class in South Asia develops, a few emergency clinics there are seeing countless typhoid fever cases among generally well-off college understudies who live in gathering family units with helpless cleanliness. [21] American clinicians should remember this, as understudies from these regions regularly go to the United States for additional schooling. [22]

Methods of Transmission:

Methods of transmission of typhoidal salmonella are:

- Oral transmission through food or refreshments is dealt with by a frequently asymptomatic individual—a transporter—who constantly sheds the microscopic organisms through stool or, less regularly through urine.
- Hand-to-mouth transmission in the wake of utilizing a defiled latrine and ignoring hand cleanliness.
- Oral transmission through sewage-defiled water or shellfish (particularly in developing countries). [10, 11, 12]

Epidemiology:

Typhoid fever happens around the world, essentially in agricultural countries whose clean conditions are poor. Typhoid fever is widespread in Asia, Oceania, the Caribbean, Latin America and Africa yet 80% of cases come from China, Bangladesh, Indonesia,

Pakistan, Nepal, Vietnam and India [25, 24]. Within those nations, typhoid fever is generally normal in immature regions. Typhoid fever contaminates generally 21.6 million individuals (occurrence of 3.6 per 1,000 populations) and murders an expected 200,000 individuals consistently. [25] Mortality or Morbidity rate with speedy and suitable anti-infection treatment, typhoid fever is ordinarily a transient febrile disease requiring a middle of 6 days of hospitalization. Treated, it has not many long haul sequelae and a 0.2% danger of mortality. [23] Untreated typhoid fever is a hazardous disease of half a month with long haul grimness frequently including the focal sensory system. The case casualty rate in the United States in the pre-anti-infection time was 9%-13%. [26]

Classic Typhoid Fever Syndrome:

The symptoms of typhoid fever observed clinically are not obvious as it begins within 7-14 days after absorption of typhoid causing *S typhi* and paratyphi organisms. The pattern of fever observed is gradual as the temperature increases day by day and dropped every next morning. Within the first week gastrointestinal manifestations started developing within the patient which include severe upper colic quadrant pain, tenderness and abdominal pain. Peyer patches were inflamed by monocytic infiltration which ultimately contract the lumen of bowel leading to constipation. [27] After first week of illness bacterial emboli on the dermis is developed in patient majorly due to non-typhoidal salmonella and shigellosis [28]. In the second week of illness, the symptoms became more severe. In the third week, patient condition grows more noxious and anorexic with substantial weight loss and abdominal swelling. In some patient liquid diarrhea which is green-yellow and smelly is observed. The patient may incline towards the typhoid state. At this stage, myocarditis, intestinal hemorrhage and overwhelming toxemia cause death. If the patient survived till fourth week then within few days the person show less severe symptoms which lead to healthy individual. [21, 29, 30, 2, 4]. The timing of the host response symptoms and may differ based on race factors, the infecting bacterial strain and geographic region. The step wise fever pattern that was once the assurance of typhoid fever now occurs in as few as 12% of cases. In most presentations of typhoid fever, the fever has a steady sneaky onset. Rather than constipation typhoid fever is developed in the children who are immunocompetent and young adults suffering from AIDS. Also, in some localities, typhoid fever is generally more apt to cause diarrhea than constipation. Typical symptoms of typhoid fever are isolated extreme headaches that can be mimic

meningitis, acute lobar pneumonia, isolated arthralgia, severe jaundice, urinary symptoms and fever. In India and Africa, some patients show neurologic indicators such as delirium and in some rare cases, Guillain-Barre and parkinsonian syndrome. Other infrequent symptoms include meningitis, pancreatitis, [31] osteomyelitis, orchitis, and abscesses in the body. [2]

Treatment and Control Measures:

If suitable treatment is commenced within the first few days of illness, the disease begins to end after about 2 days, and the patient's condition improves within 4-5 days. Any postponement raises the likelihood of complications and recovery time. A multi-drug resistant (MDR) strain of *S. Typhi* to chloramphenicol, ampicillin, and co-trimoxazole emerged in the late 1980s in Asia, and later in Africa. This has declined with the widespread use of fluoroquinolones. Unfortunately, *S. Typhi* strains with reduced sensitivity and resistance to fluoroquinolones developed in the 1990s, mainly in the Indian subcontinent[32]. Third generation cephalosporins (such as ceftriaxone and cefotaxime) are often used, particularly in patients admitted to hospital. Sporadic reports of emerging resistance to these antibiotics are of serious concern [33]. Azithromycin is used as the first-line oral treatment for typhoid fever. In most endemic areas, the control measures are related to socio-economic development which has been slow down. In addition, it needs well-functioning medical facilities to gain control of typhoid fever through antimicrobial treatment and is hampered by the antibiotic-resistant *S. Typhi* growing problem. In high-risk areas, vaccination contrary to typhoid fever is also a crucial control measure [34]. Visitors to these regions as well as household contacts of typhoid fever carriers and laboratory staff may benefit from an effective vaccine, in addition to populations residing in areas where typhoid fever is endemic[35]

REFERENCES:

- Papagrigorakis MJ, Synodinos PN, Yapijakis C. Ancient typhoid epidemic reveals the possible ancestral strain of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2007 Jan. 7(1):126-7.
- Christie AB. *Infectious Diseases: Epidemiology and Clinical Practice.* 4th ed. Edinburgh, Scotland: Churchill Livingstone; 1987.
- Raffatellu M, Chessa D, Wilson RP, Tükel C, Akçelik M, Bäumlner AJ. Capsule-mediated immune evasion: a new hypothesis explaining aspects of typhoid fever pathogenesis. *Infect Immun.* 2006 Jan. 74(1):19-27.
- Parry CM, Hien TT, Dougan G, et al. Typhoid fever. *N Engl J Med.* 2002 Nov 28. 347(22):1770-82. [Medline]. [Full Text].
- de Jong HK, Parry CM, van der Poll T, Wiersinga WJ. Host-pathogen interaction in invasive Salmonellosis. *PLoS Pathog.* 2012. 8(10):e1002933. [Medline]. [Full Text].
- Ramsden AE, Mota LJ, Münter S, Shorte SL, Holden DW. The SPI-2 type III secretion system restricts the motility of *Salmonella*-containing vacuoles. *Cell Microbiol.* 2007 Oct. 9(10):2517-29. [Medline].
- Gonzalez-Escobedo G, Gunn JS. Gallbladder epithelium as a niche for chronic *Salmonella* carriage. *Infect Immun.* 2013 Aug. 81(8):2920-30. [Medline]. [Full Text].
- Chiou CS, Wei HL, Mu JJ, Liao YS, Liang SY, Liao CH, et al. *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi variants in long-term carriers. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2013 Feb. 51(2):669-72. [Medline]. [Full Text].
- Levine MM, Tacket CO, Sztein MB. Host-*Salmonella* interaction: human trials. *Microbes Infect.* 2001 Nov-Dec. 3(14-15):1271-9. [Medline].
- Earampamoorthy S, Koff RS. Health hazards of bivalve-mollusk ingestion. *Ann Intern Med.* 1975 Jul. 83(1):107-10. [Medline]. [Full Text].
- Ali S, Vollaard AM, Widjaja S, Surjadi C, van de Vosse E, van Dissel JT. PARK2/PACRG polymorphisms and susceptibility to typhoid and paratyphoid fever. *Clin Exp Immunol.* 2006 Jun. 144(3):425-31. [Medline].
- Ram PK, Naheed A, Brooks WA, Hossain MA, Mintz ED, Breiman RF. Risk factors for typhoid fever in a slum in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2007 Apr. 135(3):458-65. [Medline].
- Kirkey A, Thompson CN, Tran Vu Thieu N, Dongol S, Le Thi Phuong T, Voong Vinh P, et al. Differential epidemiology of *Salmonella* Typhi and Paratyphi A in Kathmandu, Nepal: a matched case-control investigation in a highly endemic enteric fever setting. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2013. 7(8):e2391. [Medline]. [Full Text]
- Vollaard AM, Ali S, van Asten HA, Widjaja S, Visser LG, Surjadi C, et al. Risk factors for typhoid and paratyphoid fever in Jakarta, Indonesia. *JAMA.* 2004 Jun 2. 291(21):2607-15. [Medline].
- Gotuzzo E, Frisancho O, Sanchez J, Liendo G, Carrillo C, Black RE, et al. Association between the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome and infection with *Salmonella typhi* or *Salmonella paratyphi* in an endemic typhoid area. *Arch Intern Med.* 1991 Feb. 151(2):381-2.

16. Manfredi R, Chiodo F. Salmonella typhi disease in HIV-infected patients: case reports and literature review. *Inez Med.* 1999. 7(1):49-53. [Medline].
17. Gordon MA, Graham SM, Walsh AL, Wilson L, Phiri A, Molyneux E, et al. Epidemics of invasive Salmonella enterica serovar enteritidis and S. enterica Serovar Typhimurium infection associated with multidrug resistance among adults and children in Malawi. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2008 Apr 1. 46(7):963-9. [Medline].
18. Monack DM, Mueller A, Falkow S. Persistent bacterial infections: the interface of the pathogen and the host immune system. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2004 Sep. 2(9):747-65. [Medline].
19. van de Vosse E, Ali S, de Visser AW, Surjadi C, Widjaja S, Vollaard AM, et al. Susceptibility to typhoid fever is associated with a polymorphism in the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR). *Hum Genet.* 2005 Oct. 118(1):138-40. [Medline].
20. Poolman EM, Galvani AP. Evaluating candidate agents of selective pressure for cystic fibrosis. *J R Soc Interface.* 2007 Feb 22. 4(12):91-8. [Medline].
21. Dutta TK, Beerasha, Ghotekar LH. Atypical manifestations of typhoid fever. *J Postgrad Med.* 2001 Oct-Dec. 47(4):248-51. [Medline].
22. Arndt MB, Mosites EM, Tian M, Forouzanfar MH, Mokhdad AH, Meller M, et al. Estimating the burden of paratyphoid in Asia and Africa. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2014 Jun. 8 (6):e2925. [Medline].
23. Lynch MF, Blanton EM, Bulens S, Polyak C, Vojdani J, Stevenson J. Typhoid fever in the United States, 1999-2006. *JAMA.* 2009 Aug 26. 302(8):859-65. [Medline]
24. Chau TT, Campbell JI, Galindo CM, Van Minh Hoang N, Diep TS, Nga TT, et al. Antimicrobial drug resistance of Salmonella enterica serovar typhi in Asia and molecular mechanism of reduced susceptibility to the fluoroquinolones. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 2007 Dec. 51(12):4315-23. [Medline].
25. Crump JA, Luby SP, Mintz ED. The global burden of typhoid fever. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2004 May. 82(5):346-53. [Medline].
26. Crump JA, Ram PK, Gupta SK, Miller MA, Mintz ED. Part I. Analysis of data gaps about Salmonella enterica serotype Typhi infections in low and medium human development index countries, 1984-2005. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2008 Apr. 136(4):436-48. [Medline].
27. Mulligan TO. Typhoid fever in young children. *Br Med J.* 1971 Dec 11. 4(5788):665-7. [Medline].
28. Rahaman MM, Jamiul AK. Rose spots in shigellosis caused by Shigella dysenteriae type 1 infection. *Br Med J.* 1977 Oct 29. 2(6095):1123-4. [Medline].
29. Cunha BA. Malaria or typhoid fever: a diagnostic dilemma?. *Am J Med.* 2005 Dec. 118(12):1442-3; author reply 1443-4 [Medline].
30. Woodward TE, Smadel JE. Management of typhoid fever and its complications. *Ann Intern Med.* 1964 Jan. 60:144-57. [Medline].
31. Hermans P, Gerard M, Van Laethem Y, et al. Pancreatic disturbances and typhoid fever. *Scand J Infect Dis.* 1991. 23(2):201-5. [Medline].
32. Wain J, Hendriksen RS, Mikoleit ML, Keddy KH, Ochiai RL. Typhoid Fever. *Lancet* 2015;385(9973):1136–45
33. Kariuki S, Gordon MA, Feasey N, Parry CM. Antimicrobial resistance and management of invasive Salmonella disease. *Vaccine* 2015;33(3): C21–9.
34. World Health Organization. Typhoid vaccine: WHO position paper. *Weekly Epidemiological Record* 2008;83(6): 49–60.
35. Parry CM, Hien TT, Dougan G, White NJ, Farrar JJ. Typhoid fever. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2002; 347 (22):1770–82.